

The Relationship Between Iranian EFL Teachers' Emotional Intelligence and Critical Thinking

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Abstract

The present study was an attempt to investigate the relationship between EFL teachers' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking. To this end, 30 EFL Iranian high school teachers (15 males and 15 female), teaching English as a foreign language at ten high schools, in Kermanshah, were randomly selected. Three main instruments were utilized including Bar-on (1997) Emotional Quotient Inventory, Critical Thinking Appraisal, Form A (W-GCTA). Analysis of the data obtained through Pearson Correlation Coefficient revealed that there was a significantly positive relationship among the variables of the study. In the light of the results gained, the present study suggests some pedagogical implications for teachers and learners.

Keywords: Teachers' Emotional Intelligence; Critical Thinking

Introduction

No doubt, one of the important components in successful classrooms is highly-qualified teachers. Lowman (1996) [1] identified exemplary teachers as teachers who are likely to encourage high levels of learning in their students while also creating the positive memories of learning. He also stressed on teachers' interest as characteristics of effective teachers. However, there are various definitions for effective teachers. One might accept that the professional success of a qualified teacher depends on valued outcomes in educational systems. Therefore, to determine factors making a professionally successful teacher it is important to find general qualifications and current policy statements. By reviewing relevant literature, it could be suggested that some characteristics of teachers enhance students' learning or their performance. Thus, characteristics of the teachers are of paramount importance to be investigated. Among these characteristics, emotional intelligence and critical thinking are the most conspicuous [2]. Essentials of English language teaching. Singapore: Longman.).

Gardner (1983) [3] offered eight types of intelligence, which by personal intelligence flourishes the EI. In addition, from among the plethora of theories proposed for EI, theories of Daniel Goleman, Reuven Bar-On, Salovey and Mayer's have been the most effective in

academic circles and have helped understanding and a good knowledge of EI. According to Salovey and Mayer (1990) [4], EI is the ability of people to manage their emotions, and is the subset of social intelligence involving the ability to monitor feelings and emotions, which distinguishes between them and uses this information to manage one's thinking and action. Both *Emotional Intelligence* (1995) [5] and *Working with Emotional Intelligence* (1998) [6] of Goleman publicized EI. Schutte and Mallouff (1999) [7] opposed that Goleman's (1995) view of adaptive nature of EI was comprehended by the idea that cognitive intelligence may contribute the ones who enter educational settings; though, EI determines their achievement. Moreover, Bar-On (1997) [8] defined EI as a range of non-cognitive capabilities, skills, and competencies that influence one's ability to succeed in handling environmental stresses and pressures. Bar-On (1997), outlining the importance of EI for success in life generally, emphasized the dire need for measuring, quantifying and operationalizing EI. Later, he established a questionnaire to quantify EI and called his measure Emotional Z.

Goleman (1995) [5] defines emotional intelligence based on the ability to love and to be loved by others. Simply, specified emotional intelligence as a learned ability to recognize, understand, experience, and express human emotions healthy and productively. Emotional experience and expression are exclusive for each teacher and student. People do not think, express feelings, and choose behaviors and acts in the same way. Emotional intelligence is about using emotions and information to make a good decision; it works on emotional information in the same manner that other types of intelligence might operate.

The crucial purpose of teaching critical thinking is to assist learners make judgments based on the cautious weighing of existing facts. On the other hand, critical thinking is a very complicated issue. According to Buskist and Irons (2008) [9], such an issue requires students to learn a number of subtasks including:

- increasing a cynical approach to problem solving and decision making.
- solving various problems with simplest outcomes.
- finding proof that supports and refutes a given end.
- establishing a watchful approach toward their personal predisposition, assumptions, and standards that may obstruct to make an objective resolution.

Concerning the teaching strategies, it is assumed that ELT in Iran has been greatly affected by traditional teaching methods highlighting linguistic structures, lexicons, and inauthentic materials. Mowlaie and Rahimi (2010) [10] argue that while Iranian English teachers were acquainted with the tenets and principles of the communicative language teaching method, they did not employ it when it came to practice and preferred the conventional teaching methods in which they as the authorities presented the information and the students passively absorbed it. In the same vein, Rahimi and Chabok (2013) [11] maintain that even though Iranian EFL educators emphasized the significance of a learner-centered approach to language teaching, they were somehow willing to be the authority in their classes.

Mortiboys (2005) [12] argues that two leading factors to investigate the effect of teacher's characteristics on the EFL learners' educational achievement include emotional intelligence and critical thinking, and their teaching strategies. Emotional intelligence can increase

learners' engagement, motivation, creativity, optimistic attitudes, collaboration, and readiness for taking risks. On the other hand, critical thinking promotes the cognitive and metacognitive skills of teachers and might assist language instructors to achieve positive results in foreign languages, and any other fields [13]. According to Behak and Massari (2004) [14], the lack of critical thinking ability of teachers might inhibit to express their personal reflection. Wang (2009) [15] argues that teachers' implementation of critical thinking ability in educational contexts affects learners' satisfaction with the instructional objectives, materials, and method; they became also satisfied with the teacher's characteristics, and the condition of the context.

Many studies [16] [17] have focused on critical thinking of teachers, their emotional intelligence (EI), and their teaching strategies, yet no study has been conducted on the relationship between them in an Iranian EFL context. Thus, due to the significant impact of teacher's characteristics on students' future success, the present research is an attempt to broaden the scope of previous studies in general and delve into Iranian EFL context in particular.

teachers play an important role in learning as key contributors in learning process. Scott (1990) [18] believe that when teachers come to the job have personalities previously formed, but they have some potential attitudes and abilities to be learnt and worked on. In the same vein, Harmer (1998) [19] states that character and personality of a teacher is a central issue in the classroom. According to Bagherkazemi and Birjandi (2010) [20], critical thinking of a teacher is highly intertwined with his/her pedagogical success. Because of the close relationship between teachers' critical thinking ability and students' success, students' progress is influenced by critical thinking of teacher which is highly interconnected with educational success. In addition, Goleman (1995) [5] states that the majority of a person's successes in life are based on his/her emotional intelligence. Additionally, according to Sharma and Bindal (2012) [21], there is an important relationship between teachers' EI and their professional success and thereby extremely affect students' achievement. What is of paramount importance in foreign language acquisition is examining the possible link between teachers' critical thinking and their EI that can have unresolved effects on education programs, syllabus designs and adapting methods of teacher for increasing the students' success.

According to Ennis (1987), good thinking is critical thinking, which he defined it as: a reasonable reflective thinking dedicated to decide what to believe or do. In the same vein, Elizabeth, May and Chee (2008) [22] asserted that the ability to promote critical thinking was fundamental in teachers' effectiveness. Furthermore, the most important factor for effective leaders in the workplace is emotional intelligence [23]. Brown (2007) [24] regards emotions as dominators of all our thought, actions, and reflections. He believes that we are influenced by our emotions.

Salovey and Mayer (1990) [25] considered EI as the ability to identify, generate and understand emotions to help thinking and control emotions thoughtfully in order to improve emotional and intellectual growth. In the same line, Saeidi and Yusefi (2008) [26] suggested

that emotional intelligence consisted of the abilities to bring forth the optimal results in the relationships between the person and others.

Lewis and Smith (1993) [27] state that roots of critical thinking are in two main academic disciplines: philosophy and psychology. Sternberg (1986) [28] has also referred a third critical thinking discipline in the field of education.

The Philosophical Approach

Many philosophers (e.g. Aristotle, Richard Paul) demonstrate the philosophical approach. The focus of this approach is on the hypothetical critical thinker, computing the qualities and characteristics of this person rather than the activities or actions the critical thinker can perform. According to Sternberg (1986) [28], this school of thought approaches the critical thinker as an ideal type, concentrating on what people can do under the best of circumstances.

about how people really think.

The Educational Approach

Lastly, those participated in discussions about critical thinking are working in the field of education. This category includes Benjamin Bloom and his associates. one of the most broadly cited sources for educational practitioners is their classification for information processing skills (1956) [29] when it comes to teaching and measuring higher-order thinking skills. Bloom's classification is classified, with "understanding" at the bottom and "assessment" at the top. The three highest levels (analysis, synthesis, and evaluation) are often said to signify critical thinking.

Unlike both the logical and the psychological traditions, the advantage of the educational approach is the years of classroom experience and observations of student learning. Though, it is noted that the educational approach is narrow in its vagueness. Concepts within the taxonomy have no clarity necessary to guide instruction and assessment in a valuable way. Furthermore, Sternberg (1986) maintains that the frameworks established in education have not been verified as vigorously as those established within either philosophy or psychology. Along with the heart of emotional intelligence theory is the once-queer theory that two attached axes are emotion and reason and supporters of overall success in different life areas. roots of Ignorance of emotions is in the ideology of early philosophers such as Aristotle, and negative view held at the opposing role of affective factors in human development which had brought about permanent harms, mainly in the education area. Certainly, the initiation of EI as a modern psychological theory contributed put an end to such harmful and injurious views, and as a result, it helped pedagogy to pass in a new unparalleled phase.

Age of individualism was introduced at second half of the twentieth century, when individual ideals and differences were accepted and respected. After a prolonged concern with the physical features of man, the tide turned and attention was focused on the human being as entirety of physical, cognitive and affective variables. Man became man in the real sense of the word. This shift of focus was on the view of education.

One characteristic of every individual deals with emotional variables. According to Brown (2007) [24], well-organized mental and cognitive processing is controlled by the

management of core emotions. As Goleman (1995) [5] stated, the emotional mind is closer than the rational mind, skipping into action without even stopping to find what it is doing. On the other hand, seemingly, emotions have been usually ignored, learning and teacher training progresses although the recent research on emotional intelligence (EI) caused radical changes.

Human is extremely emotional and emotions control thought, actions and images. Actually, human is influenced by his emotion. It means that emotionally intelligent individuals could help less emotionally intelligent individuals in how to manage emotions [30]. Findings showed that, the employee's emotional intelligence play more important role than skills, knowledge and genetic traits for effective performance [31].

According to Barchard and Hakstian (2004) [32], emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize and control the emotions. Emotional intelligence is defined as a set of skills assumed to help the exact appraisal and expression of emotion in oneself and in others and is regulation of the emotion in self and others, and the applying feelings and emotions to increase inspiration, developing and implementing plans, and achieving the predetermined objectives. Bora (2012) [33] found that students with high levels of emotional intelligence were more participated in speaking and brain-based activities, because of high levels of self-esteem and social skills, and could cooperate with others. They also showed that students who had low level of emotional intelligence had weak relations with the society; so they were isolated from the classroom atmosphere, and left without taking part in speaking and brain-based activities. Some studies showed an important relationship between students' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking skills. Findings revealed that flexibility and social responsibility were among the components of emotional intelligence with highest correlations with critical thinking.

Salovey and Mayer (1990) [25] introduced the concept of emotional intelligence as "the ability to study one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to differentiate between them and to use this information to conduct one's philosophy and proceedings". Additionally, Ahuja (2011) [34] refer to the employees with better understanding themselves and others and better managing their feelings and respond along with the situation will certainly perform better in their jobs. Stress management, general mood, intrapersonal adaptability, and interpersonal are components of emotional.

Emotional Intelligence Models

1 Bar-On Model of Emotional-Social Intelligence (ESI)

EI has defined by Bar-On (1997) [8] as "an array of non-cognitive abilities, competencies, and skills that effect on individual's ability to succeed in coping with environmental difficulties and pressures" (p.11). Bar-On's model of emotional intelligence regards to the potential for act and success, rather than act or success itself by considering the process-oriented rather than outcome-oriented. Its focus is on an array of emotional and social capabilities, as well as the ability to be aware of, comprehend, and express oneself, the ability to be aware of, comprehend, and relate to others, the ability to cope with strong emotions, and the ability to adjust to change and solve problems of a social or personal

nature. BarOn (2006) [35] describes emotional intelligence based on such emotional and social skills that encourage our understanding and expression of ourselves, our understanding for others and communication with them, and the ability to cope with everyday stresses. He considers five major components and 15 subscales of these components which are defined below:

a. Intrapersonal Component

The intrapersonal part of emotional intelligence highlights self-awareness and self-expression. It contains following five subscales:

-*Emotional Self-Awareness*: includes the awareness and accepting of one's own emotions.

-*Self-Regard*: includes the acceptance, understanding and respect of the self.

-*Self-Actualization*: regards to the ability to attempt for personal purposes and actualize one's potentials.

-*Assertiveness*: is the ability to efficiently express and protect one's beliefs and thoughts.

-*Independence*: is being self-directed and self-control ability.

b. Interpersonal Component:

The interpersonal part of emotional intelligence model is focused on social-awareness and interpersonal interactions. It has following subscales:

-*Empathy*: is the ability to find and understand others feelings.

-*Social Responsibility*: is the ability of being a constructive, cooperative and accountable member of the society.

-*Interpersonal Relationships*: express the ability to create pleasant relationships and healthy interaction with others.

c. Stress Management:

This component of EI includes controlling and regulating emotions and involves two sub-scales of:

Stress Tolerance: is the ability to hold out the hard conditions and unpleasant events by constructively managing emotions.

Impulse Control: is the ability against a desire, a determination or a temptation by directing one's emotions.

d. Adaptability:

This component of EI model is concerned with the ability to modify the change and cope with the difficulties that come with the change. It contains following sub-scales:

-*Reality Testing*: is the ability to accurately judge the external reality and the internal feelings.

-*Flexibility*: is the ability to adjust one's thoughts and emotions along with the changing situations and change in new situations.

-*Problem Solving*: is the ability to recognize the problem and to present an effective solution.

e. General Mood

This component of emotional intelligence contains the abilities related to self-motivation. It contains two sub-scales:

-*Happiness*: refers to the agreement with one's life, and the ability to direct positive feelings and enjoy life.

-*Optimism*: is the ability to think positively, to keep in view the bright side of the life and continue hopeful in the face of problems and negative feelings.

.2 A Mixed Model of Emotional Intelligence: Goleman Model

Daniel Goleman (1998) proposed a model with focusing on EI as a wide array of capabilities and skills that determine the leadership performance. Goleman's model outlines four main emotional intelligence concepts and 20 skills.

1. *Self-Awareness* contains three competences: Self-Confidence, Emotional Self-Awareness, and Accurate Self-Assessment.

2. *Self-Management* contains six competences: Self-Control, Dependability, Conscientiousness, Adaptability, Success Drive and Initiative.

3. *Social Awareness* contains three competencies: Understanding, Service Orientation and Organizational Awareness.

4. Relationship Management contains eight competences: Developing Others, Effect, Communication, Conflict Management, Leadership, Change Catalyst, Building Bonds and Teamwork and Collaboration.

Goleman(1998) [6] states that self-awareness is the ability to read one's emotions and identify their effects while using gut feelings to guide decisions. The second construct is Self-management includes controlling one's emotions and impulses and adjusts to changing circumstances. Social awareness is the third one includes the ability to sense, understand, and respond to other's emotions while understanding social networks. Lastly, relationship management, the fourth construct, involves the ability to motivate, influence, and develop others while managing conflict.

3 Trait EI Model

According to Petrides and Furnham (2001) [36] trait EI is "a collection of emotional self-perceptions positioned at the lower levels of personality" (p.17) . Actually, they maintain that trait EI related to an individual's self-perceptions of their emotional abilities. The characterization of EI includes both behavioral dispositions and self-perceived skills, measured by self-report measures. Trait EI is encompassed of "behavioral dispositions and self-perceived skills" and should be measured through self-report questionnaires, and is referred to the study of personality.

according to Abdullahi (2001) [37], teachers who have acceptable emotional intelligence skills can generate an enjoyable classroom by having a dynamic group conversation with the students. In each learning process, they can decrease the negative effect of students' anxiety by creating a standard and pleasurable condition with psychological supporting the students.

According to Scriven and Paul (2004) [38] , critical thinking is mode of thinking about any topic, content, or issue, by improving the quality of thinking by competently taking charge of the constructions essential in thinking and imposing intellectual standards upon them.

Ricketts and Rudd (2004) [39] define three aspects of critical thinking disposition:

- *Cognitive Maturity*: tendency of students to finding opportunities to use reasoning; anticipating situations that need reasoning; and confidence in reasoning ability.

- *Engagement*: tendency of students to be intellectually interested and desire to know the truth.

- *Innovativeness*: tendency of students to know the complexity of the problems; being open to other perspectives; and know their own and others biases and tendencies.

methodology

The main purpose of the present study was to investigate the relationship between EFL teachers' emotional intelligence, their critical thinking,..

Due to research question and the nature of the study itself, the current research was carried out quantitatively, and correlational research design was administered. In such doing, the relationship among variables including emotional intelligence, critical thinking, were investigated.

The participants consisted of 30 EFL Iranian high school teachers (15 male and 15 female), teaching English as a foreign language at ten high schools, in Kermanshah, Iran. Most of them held Bachelor degree (N=21) and the rest Master degree (N=9). Due to the importance of accessibility criteria for subject selection, convenience random sampling was conducted. They range between 28-36 years old. In addition, they were ensured that all of the obtained information was kept confidential and only used for the purpose of the present research. Table..1. illustrates the demographic information of the participants.

Table.1Demographic Information of the Participants.

Group	Characteristics	Number of Participants	Frequenc y
	Male	15	50%
	Gender	Female	15
			50%
EFL	Teaching	1-3	11
			26.8%
High	Experience	4-6	17
School		above 6	38.7%
Teachers			12
			27.3%
	Academic	B.A.	21
			68.1%

Instrumentations

two main instruments were used in the present research.

Bar-On (1997) Emotional Quotient Inventory

As the first instrument of the study and in order to evaluate EFL teachers' emotional intelligence, the "Bar-On EI test," put forward by Bar-on (1980) [40], was utilized. According to Bar-On (1997) [8], this test was considered as a self-report measure of emotionally and socially intelligent behavior that provided a reliable and standard measurement to investigate emotional-social intelligence of individuals. For the purpose of the present study, the Persian version of the test, validated by Dehshiri (2003) was conducted. This test, in a Likert scale ranged from "Very Seldom True" to "Very Often True" and estimated the following characteristics:

- a. intrapersonal including, emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, independence, self-actualization), self-regard.
- b. interpersonal including social responsibility, interpersonal relationship, empathy,
- c. Adaptability including reality testing, flexibility, problem solving,
- d. Stress management including impulse control, stress tolerance, general mood components, optimism, happiness of people.

According to Dehshiri (2003) [41], *emotional quotient inventory* and its subcomponents do have reliability and validity in Iranian EFL context and its was calculated (0.73). However, this scale was also reviewed by three language experts to ensure its validity, and their comments were utilized in the final version of the scale.

Critical Thinking Appraisal-Form A (W-GCTA)

W-GCTA, introduced by Watson and Glaser (1980) [42], included five subcomponents which practically examined the 5 characteristics of an individual as a critical thinker:

- a. Recognition of assumptions
- b. Drawing inferences
- c. Making deductions
- d. Evaluating arguments
- e. Interpreting evidence to decide if conclusions are legitimate or not

According to Watson and Glaser (1980) [42], its reliability was calculated to be ($r=0.83$). The W-GCTA consists of eighty statements followed by 2 to 5 alternatives. To ensure its validity, it was reviewed by three language experts. . It should be noted here that few studies (e.g. Schutte & Mallouff, 1999; Mortibuys, 2005) [43] [12] have utilized this instrument to evaluate critical thinking ability.

Data Analysis

The data in this study was analyzed using SPSS²¹ through three sections to respond to the research questions. First, descriptive statistics (frequency, mean and standard deviation) were used to address the research questions. These questions addressed whether there was

any meaningful relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' emotional intelligence, their critical thinking ability,. Utilizing SPSS, to analyze the data Pearson correlation coefficient was conducted.

The research question was seeking to explore whether there was any meaningful relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking ability. To this end, the results of the Emotional Quotient Inventory and Critical Thinking Appraisal-Form A (W-GCTA) were analyzed by conducting Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Table2. illustrates the results.

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Coefficient for Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Critical Thinking Ability (CTA).

		Emotional Intelligence	Critical Thinking Ability
EI	Pearson Correlation	1	.280**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
CTA	Pearson Correlation	.280**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As the data in Table 2,show, the Pearson correlation coefficient is .28 being relatively high. On the other hand, since p-value is less than .01 (sig=.000), it is concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between EFL Iranian teachers' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking ability, thereby answering the first research question and rejecting the first null hypothesis, as well.

Conclusion

The current study was set to explore whether there was any relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking ability. The findings of Pearson Correlation Coefficients revealed that there was a significantly positive relationship among the variables of the study. That is to say, there was a statistically positive relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' emotional intelligence and their critical thinking ability. In fact, when the teachers possess a high level of EI, they have a better critical thinking ability.

The findings of the current study are in line with a number of studies (e.g., Carmeli, 2003; Ross, 1994; Schutte et al., 1998) [44] [45] [46] ; however, research on the relationship between these variables among the teachers is still meager. In addition, Mortiboys (2005) [12] maintained that the way the teachers manipulate their emotions would enhance the chances of the students' engagement, motivation, and collaboration.

According to Nias (1996) [47], teaching in general and teaching a second/foreign language in particular involve human interaction and thus has an emotional dimension. Nelson and Low (2005) [48] argue that one of the thorniest major problems for the learners in academic contexts is to provide a safe environment that is emotionally healthy and challenging. Making a healthy learning context focused on personal, academic, and career excellence requires an understanding and emphasis on affective as well as cognitive skills [13]. As mentioned earlier, studying affective characteristics of instructors and teachers is one promising area of research that assist effective teaching implementation.

The results of the present study are also consistent with some other studies (e.g. Emig, 1997, Haley, 2004 & Hamurlu, 2007) [49] [50] [51] . They indicated that multiple intelligence-based teaching affected both EFL learners' language achievement and their positive attitude towards language learning experience. All these confirm that higher emotional intelligence not only affects teachers' instruction and formulates their attitudes which finally paves the ground for their teaching and facilitates learning but it also affects what learners think and feel in the learning process and assist them to develop positive attitude which again affects their learning.

The results are also in line with Khodabakhshzadeh and Ghaemi's (2011) [52] research. They explored the relationship between teachers' critical thinking and their teaching success. Their results revealed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' critical thinking and their achievement.

Reviewing the existing literature, the relationship between emotional intelligence and critical thinking ability has been shown in various studies. As mentioned before, although these studies are quite scant and concern predominantly with first language contexts, the findings are consistent with the results of the current research. For example. Brackett and Katluka (2007) [53] argued that emotional intelligence would also enhance overall academic learning by increasing abstract reasoning and critical thinking ability.

Viewing from learners' life perspective, it is apparent that the world is changing rapidly and that the new issues arise and the old ones are revisited. Wright (2002) [54] maintains that educational advancement should respond to these by making reflective and reasonable decisions which entail reacting flexibly changes in educational contexts. Facione (2010) [55] posited that an ideal critical thinker possesses several features, including flexibility in considering alternative and opinions, and prudence in suspending, altering or revising judgments.

Conclusion

The main conclusion addresses the importance of both emotional intelligence and critical thinking for the EFL teachers. Thus, officials and educators who are responsible for

constructing higher education should provide facilities for holding some workshops, conferences and teacher training courses (TTCs) for university instructors, at least for the less experienced ones, in which the concepts of emotional intelligence and critical thinking would be presented, and their significance in effective teaching and the development of teacher professional success would be discussed, and the strategies for their further development be proposed. No doubt, both EI and CT constructs are complicated and consist of multilayered variables for which some more replications are required. Thus, when the interaction between one of these variables with another complex one is the matter of investigation, more cautions should be taken into account.

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